

Power Simulation Program: An Adaptable Application for Assessment of Power in Planning and Pre-Data Analysis of Clinical Study Data—An MTBI² Study

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Abstract

Power analyses represent a key component in the design of clinical studies and the detection of significant findings from them. Current statistical packages allow for calculating power and sample size under a variety of study assumptions. We propose a tool for calculating power given more specific assumptions. Study data given these assumptions are generated using simulation, with R software, including outcome, treatment, covariates, and distributional characteristics among these. A model is fit to the study data such that a treatment effect is assessed and a t-statistic is obtained. Data are resampled, the model is refit, and t-statistics of the treatment effect are obtained using bootstrap. Power is calculated based on the proportion of t-statistics exceeding a critical value corresponding with a significant test. We applied this tool to assess power under assumptions for clinical studies assessing therapies for symptoms caused by mild traumatic brain injury (mTBI). The program tool can be adapted for different study designs. It is potentially a useful planning and pre-data analysis tool for researchers.

Key Words: power, simulation, clinical trial design, statistical analysis, sample size

1. Introduction

Background and Purpose of Research

Developing analytic tools is crucial for the design and analysis of studies for mild traumatic brain injury (mTBI). Study assumptions may change over a study period, which then requires a re-evaluation of the study design, including study power. According to Dorey (2010), power is the probability that the researcher will correctly reject the null hypothesis. When one hears of statistical power, the next thought is generally what sample size for the research study will provide a good enough power value for the main hypothesis being tested. In general, sample size, effect size, and power are closely related to each other, and if one knows any two of them, then the third can be determined.

Generally, current statistical packages for calculating power require information for the expected effect size, sample size, and significance level used for a given statistical test. Other packages allow for more flexibility with respect to planning and study assumptions. For example, PROC GLMPOWER in SAS includes options for evaluating power for longitudinal and multi-level analyses (SAS Institute Inc., Cary NC). Methods for calculating power based on

simulated data may offer wider flexibility compared with available packages. The potential advantage of these methods compared with options using standard software tools is that simulated data can be tailored to more directly represent actual study data one plans to analyze (Ma et al. 2016; Morris et al, 2017; Huang et al, CCT 2022).

Strategies that use simulation for calculating power estimates are widespread. A search based on keywords “statistical power analysis simulation based” indicated roughly 100 articles on this topic. Strategies vary but share a common feature: to more accurately represent the underlying study data and research question of interest for a more accurate calculation of study power. Arnold et al. (2011) applied simulation to calculate power given a complex sampling design for a proposed clinical trial. Ma et al. (2016) created a simulation-based sample size calculator to provide a less biased over-estimate of power, by increasing the measurement frequency in participants with high risk of declining health status or changing risk exposures. Beng et al. (2021) evaluated power using different cohort sizes by running an M simulation in a large set of simulated patients with total knee arthroplasty. Ensor et al. (2018) estimated power for planned Individual Participant Data (IPD) meta-analysis projects by using simulation-based power calculations. Kumle et al. (2021) conducted simulation-based power analyses by first simulating new datasets and analyzing each dataset for statistical significance, using available packages in R.

A similar motivation underlies the application of simulation-based approaches for examining power for clinical trials. For example, these trials may depend on outcome measures that are non-normal, or for which the variability of the outcome measures differ across time or vary by treatment group, or for which the underlying covariance patterns in patients may vary with respect to time and/or treatment group. Additionally, simulation-based approaches may be able to accommodate methods that have been shown to improve the precision of the treatment effect (Colantuoni et al., 2015). Whether the motivation for applying these approaches is to address particular situations of clinical trials (e.g., multiple primary endpoints, covariate adjustment) (Colantuoni et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2022), or to assess sensitivity of power estimates given underlying study characteristics (Lane and Hennes, 2019), simulation-based approaches potentially offer flexibility and improved estimation of power in clinical trial design.

We propose a power simulation program that combines R software capabilities, simulated study data depending on what study characteristics the user chooses to specify and parameters necessary for calculating power. In this paper, we provide the R program that we developed and also show its application in three different clinical trials administered by the Military Traumatic Brain Injury Initiative (MTBI²).

2. Methods

All analyses were conducted and the power simulation program was created using R Statistical Software v4.2.1 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria). First, a data-generating model is applied based on protocol assumptions and findings from previous clinical trials. Given study characteristics, we may include different study parameter assumptions including: 1) mean of primary outcome variable at each timepoint (assuming a longitudinal design); 2) between-group mean difference in primary outcome variable, where groups are those participants receiving treatment or control; 3) variability of primary outcome variable; 4) within-subject correlation of primary outcome variable; and 5) sample size. The specification of different study parameters is illustrated with an example below (**Figure 1**), which assumes constant variability and within-subject correlation of the primary outcome variable. The program can be modified to include more complexity with respect to these different parameters. Following this, a random multivariate normal distribution of the study outcome measure is generated separately for the treatment and control groups (**Figure 2**). One can specify different variance-covariance matrices with respect to these groups as well. An allocation ratio of 3:1 is assumed for the two groups (treatment group N=75, control group N=25). The next series of steps involve formatting the simulated data with the end goal of transforming the data from wide format to long format for performing longitudinal analysis in R (**Figure 3**). Pertinent variables are added for the purposes of the analysis – i.e., Subject ID, a treatment indicator variable, and indicator variables to represent discrete timepoints (i.e., baseline, post-treatment evaluation, follow-up evaluation).

Figure 1. Data-Generation using the power simulation program¹.

```
corr <- 0.8

mu1c <- 17.8
mu2c <- 14.6
mu3c <- 11.4

mu1t <- 17.0
mu2t <- 14.0-2
mu3t <- 11.0-2

sigma1 <- 5.5
sigma2 <- 5.5
sigma3 <- 5.5

sigma1sq <- sigma1^2
sigma2sq <- sigma2^2
sigma3sq <- sigma3^2

covariance_12 <- sigma1*sigma2*corr
covariance_13 <- sigma1*sigma3*corr
covariance_23 <- sigma2*sigma3*corr
```

¹ R code above indicates the specification of different parameters for initially generating a set of simulated data used in the program. A study with three timepoints (patient visits) is assumed. ‘corr’ represents the within-subject correlation for the primary outcome variable. The mean values (mu1c, mu2c, mu3c) represent the control group mean values of the primary outcome variable at Visits 1, 2, 3 respectively. Similarly, the mean values (mu1t, mu2t, mu3t) represent the treatment group mean values of the primary outcome variable at Visits 1, 2, 3, respectively. Standard deviations for the primary outcome variable (sigma1, sigma2, sigma3) are assumed to be constant at each of the visits. Covariance values (covariance_12, covariance_13, and covariance_23) represent the covariance between Visit 1 and 2, covariance between Visit 1 and 3, and covariance between Visit 2 and 3, respectively. Note that an additional decrement ($\Delta = -2$) in the mean of the primary outcome variable is assumed for the treatment group at Visit 2 and Visit 3.

Figure 2. Data-Generation of multivariate normal study outcome response in treatment and control groups¹.

```
### Simulate control group dataframe [25x3]
set.seed(50)

dat_c <- mvnrm(25, mu=c(mu1c,mu2c,mu3c), Sigma=matrix(c(sigma1sq, covariance_12, covariance_13,
covariance_12, sigma2sq, covariance_23, covariance_13, covariance_23, sigma3sq), ncol=3, byrow=TRUE),
empirical=TRUE)

### Repeat simulation for Treatment group [75x3]
set.seed(50)

dat_t <- mvnrm(75, mu=c(mu1t,mu2t,mu3t), Sigma=matrix(c(sigma1sq, covariance_12, covariance_13,
covariance_12, sigma2sq, covariance_23, covariance_13, covariance_23, sigma3sq), ncol=3, byrow=TRUE),
empirical=TRUE)
```

¹ Generates multivariate normal primary outcome variable response for Visit 1, Visit 2, and Visit 3 in the treatment and control groups using the mvnrm() function available in R. set.seed() allows results to be reproduced. For the simulation, a 3:1 group allocation is assumed for the treatment and control groups. The dimensions [Row x Column] of each generated data frame are shown.

Figure 3. Combining simulated control and treatment group data with additional labeling variables to form the final simulated dataset¹.

```

### Create a treatment indicator variable (1/0) and add this as a fourth column in the data
trt <- rep(0,25)
dat_c <- cbind(dat_c, trt)

trt <- rep(1, 75)
dat_t <- cbind(dat_t, trt)

### Concatenate simulated Control_group and Treatment_group data[100x4].
combinegroups <- rbind(dat_c, dat_t)

### Add Subject_ID variable [100x5]
subjectid <- seq(1:100)
df<- cbind(combinegroups, subjectid)
df2 <- as.data.frame(df)

###Create separate dataframes to represent Visits=1,2,3 and add time indicator variables(Time2=1 for Visit2,
###0 o.w.; Time3=1 for Visit 3, 0 o.w.)
time2 <-rep(0,100)
time3 <-rep(0,100)
Time1 <- cbind(df2$V1, df2$trt, df2$subjectid, time2, time3) # [100x5]

time2 <-rep(1,100)
time3 <-rep(0,100)
Time2 <- cbind(df2$V2, df2$trt, df2$subjectid, time2, time3) # [100x5]

time2 <-rep(0,100)
time3 <-rep(1,100)
Time3 <- cbind(df2$V3, df2$trt,df2$subjectid, time2, time3) # [100x5]

### Concatenate Time1, Time2, and Time3 dataframes into a single dataframe [300x5]
dfnew <- rbind(Time1, Time2, Time3)dfnew2<- as.data.frame(dfnew)

### Renamed variabnames(dfnew2) <- c("Y", "Trt", "SubjectID", "Time2", "Time3")

### Final Simulated Dataset [300x5]
dfnew3 <- dfnew2[order(dfnew2$SubjectID, dfnew2$Time2, dfnew2$Time3),]
length(dfnew3[,1])
dfnew3[1:10,]

```

¹ The dimensions [Row x Column] of each generated data frame are shown.

For the analysis, a model to address the research question of interest is assumed. The research question is: Is there a difference in the change in the mean of the outcome variable between baseline and post-treatment in the treatment group *relative to* the control group? In the model, **Y** represents the outcome variable, **Trt** represents an indicator variable (1=treatment 0=control), **Time2** represents an indicator variable for the first post-treatment evaluation, **Time3** represents an indicator variable for the second post-treatment evaluation. **Trt:Time2** and **Trt:Time3** are interaction terms that represent differences in change in Y between baseline and the respective follow-up evaluations in the treatment *relative to* the control group. Baseline is represented when both Time2=0 and Time3=0.

$$lmer(Y \sim Trt + Time2 + Time3 + Trt:Time2 + Trt:Time3 + (1|SubjectID), data = dfnew3)$$

The linear mixed effect model above assesses the difference in change over time of the primary outcome variable in the treatment relative to the control group using lmer() function in R with a random effect for subject (**1|SubjectID**). No participant drop out is assumed, therefore, each subject has 3 rows of data – one for each of the three visits.

For our specific question, Trt:Time2 in the model represents the treatment effect of interest. We can assess this effect by fitting the model above to the simulated data and by evaluating the significance of the effect assuming a two-sided test and significance level $\alpha=0.05$. *Note: under this assumption, a t-statistic > critical value 1.96 corresponds with a significant test.*

The last portion of the program illustrates how data are resampled from the original simulated data, the same model above is refit to the resampled data, and t-statistics for the treatment effect Trt:Time2 are obtained over $i = 1, \dots, 1000$ replications (**Figure 4**). Based on the pool of t-statistics that are obtained, power to detect a significant effect for Trt:Time2 is calculated based on the proportion of t-statistics > 1.96—i.e., the proportion of t-statistics that represent a significant test. For the simulation above, the power value is 0.70. An R program of the code included in Figures 1-4 accompanies this paper.

Figure 4. Bootstrap and Refitting of Model to Data portion

```
library(lme4)

### Set up the t-value replicates
tval <- rep(NA, 1000)
### Set up the number of bootstrap replicates
B <- 1000

### Set the sample size
n1 <- 100

# BOOTSTRAP RESAMPLING
set.seed(500)
for(i in 1:B) {
  ### Create the sampling dataset
  ids1 <- sample(n1, n1, replace=T)
  ### Sample that will be used to fit the treatment model
  dfnew3_subset <- dfnew3[rep(ids1*3, each=3) - rep(c(2,1,0),3),]

  ### Linear Mixed Effects Model
  model1 <- lmer(Y ~ Trt + Time2 + Time3 + Trt:Time2 + Trt:Time3 +
    (1|SubjectID), data=dfnew3_subset)

  ### Extracting t-value from the summary of the lmer model
  tval[i] <- coef(summary(model1)) [17]
}

###Proportion of t-statistics > critical value 1.96 representing a significant test
power <- length(tval[abs(tval)>1.96])/length(tval)
print(power)
```

3. Applications

3.1 Sleep Healthy Using the Internet (SHUTi) Study

The MBTI² Sleep Healthy Using the Internet (SHUTi) study was a randomized controlled trial (RCT) of internet-guided, electronic cognitive behavioral therapy for insomnia (eCBT-I) in military service members (SMs) with a history of mTBI (National Library of Medicine [NLM], NCT04377009). The objective of the study was to compare the change in the primary outcome measure, Insomnia Severity Index (ISI), between the eCBT-I treatment group and the educational study control group. The allocation ratio for treatment and control groups was 3:1. The power simulation program was used to determine power under varying assumed levels of study recruitment (i.e., study sample size (N)).

The parameters used in the program application of SHUTi were:

- Between-group mean difference in ISI: $\Delta = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$
- Variability of ISI: SD = 5.5
- Within-subject correlation of ISI = 0.6, 0.7, 0.8
- Sample size: N = 200, 160, 140, 120, 110, 100

We assessed the power for the combination of 6 different sample sizes, 5 different mean differences, and 3 different within-subject correlations (a total of 90 combinations). From the 6 power graph figures in **Figure 5**, we found that when the mean difference between the $\Delta ISI_{\text{treatment}}$ and the $\Delta ISI_{\text{control}}$ is 1 or 2, only 1) an N of 200, mean difference of 2, and within-subject correlation of 0.7 or 0.8 and 2) an N of 160, mean difference of 2, and within-subject correlation of 0.7 or 0.8 had robust power values (i.e., power ≥ 0.8). All the other combinations with a mean difference of 1 or 2 produced a power value below 0.8. When the mean difference between the $\Delta ISI_{\text{treatment}}$ and the $\Delta ISI_{\text{control}}$ was ≥ 3 , the power values of all the possible combinations were found to be ≥ 0.8 . Our power simulation program allowed us to formulate these power curves that provided insight with respect to how different parameters, especially sample size (i.e., varying recruitment levels), could affect study power.

Figure 5. SHUTi Power Simulation Results¹

¹ When the mean difference between the $\Delta ISI_{\text{treatment}}$ and the $\Delta ISI_{\text{control}}$ is 1 or 2, the majority of the power values were <0.8 . When the mean difference between the $\Delta ISI_{\text{treatment}}$ and the $\Delta ISI_{\text{control}}$ was ≥ 3 , the power values of all the possible combinations were found to be ≥ 0.8 .

3.2 Application to Combat Depression and Concussion (ACDC) Study

The Application to Combat Depression and Concussion (ACDC) clinical trial is a study of the first cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) mobile application that was developed to counteract depressive symptoms in civilians and military SMs/veterans with a history of mTBI (NLM, NCT05147506). It is the first randomized controlled trial in the field to our knowledge. The objective of this study is to measure the mean difference in the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9), which assesses degree of depression severity via a questionnaire. The allocation ratio for active CBTi digital therapeutics (DTx) treatment to control DTx group was 1:1. We used the power simulation program to determine power, given an assumed treatment effect model with (full model) and without (reduced model) baseline PHQ-9 as a covariate.

The parameters used to simulate the data in the program were:

- Between-group mean difference in PHQ-9 at baseline and 12 weeks, respectively: $\Delta = 0, \Delta = 3$
- Variability of PHQ-9: SD = 5, 6
- Within-subject correlation of PHQ-9 = 0.6, 0.7, 0.8
- Sample size: N = 36 per group

We also compared how a larger PHQ-9 standard deviation (i.e. greater variability) would impact power versus a smaller PHQ-9 standard deviation, and different assumed levels of within-subject correlation of PHQ-9 between baseline and the 12-week visit. In **Table 1**, we see that the full model that adjusts the treatment effect for the baseline covariate PHQ-9 provides more robust power values compared to the reduced model of treatment alone. Given that participants have varying baseline PHQ-9 levels which are reflected in the PHQ-9 measure at 12 weeks, accounting for these baseline differences (between-subject variability) addresses this variability in the 12-week measure. As a result, a more precise estimate of the treatment effect at the 12-week assessment is obtained resulting in greater power. Notably, power remained robust (~ 0.80) despite imposing increased variability in PHQ-9 ($\sigma=6$) and reduced within-subject correlation between baseline and follow-up ($\text{corr}=0.6$).

Table 1. ACDC Power Simulation Results¹

Simulation study parameters ($\Delta = 3, \sigma=5, \text{corr} = 0.6-0.8,$ N per group = 36)	Model 1 (trt only)	Model 2 (trt + covar)
corr = 0.6	0.76	0.91
0.7	0.76	0.95
0.8	0.76	0.99

Simulation study parameters ($\Delta = 3, \sigma =6, \text{corr} = 0.6-0.8,$ N per group = 36)	Model 1 (trt only)	Model 2 (trt + covar)
corr = 0.6	0.60	0.78

0.7	0.60	0.87
0.8	0.61	0.95

¹Comparison of Model 1 (treatment only) and Model 2 (treatment + baseline covariate PHQ-9). For the simulation, between-group difference at 12 weeks (treatment vs. control) $\Delta=3$, PHQ-9 SD (σ)=5,6, and within-subject correlation (corr)=0.6-0.8 were assumed. Linear Model 1) $Y \sim \text{Trt}$ and linear Model 2) $Y \sim \text{Trt} + \text{Baseline PHQ-9}$ were fit to the simulated data where Y represented PHQ-9 at 12 weeks. Based on comparable programming steps shown in Figure 4, the bootstrap used for this simulation included 1000 replicates where the t-statistics for the treatment effect 'Trt' for each model was examined assuming a two-sided test and $\alpha=0.05$.

3.3 Calcitonin Gene-Related Peptide (CGRP) Monoclonal Antibody (Erenumab) Phase 2 trial

The Calcitonin Gene-Related Peptide (CGRP) Monoclonal Antibody (Erenumab) Phase 2 trial is a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, multicenter 12-week study followed by a 4-week open-label safety extension study (NLM, NCT05049057). It is for military SMs and civilians who have acute post-traumatic headache (PTH) with a history of mTBI. The objective of this study was to compare the effect of erenumab versus the placebo on the number of monthly headache days for participants at Weeks 8 to 12 of the study. Visit 1 represents the assessment of the outcome (monthly headache days) from Weeks 0-4; Visit 2 represents Weeks 4-8; and Visit 3 represents Weeks 8-12. The last timepoint of the study was chosen as the primary outcome because the effective dosage level of the drug was expected to reach its maximum at this visit.

In addition, given patients with acute PTH were enrolled within 7-days of their TBI, no baseline data of monthly headache frequency were collected. Patients were randomized to treatment or placebo and monthly headache days were assessed for the visit periods indicated above. The allocation ratio for the treatment versus the control group was 1:1. The recruitment ratio of men: women was 70:30. The treatment effect of the trial assumed this ratio and a 50:50 ratio of patients with chronic versus episodic headache. Study assumptions included expected differences in treatment effect given the greater prevalence of migraine headaches in women compared with men (Peterlin, 2011). In addition, erenumab was expected to lower the number of monthly headache days at different rates for those participants with episodic versus chronic headache.

The power simulation program was applied to the CGRP trial for two reasons: 1) to evaluate power under varying assumptions of the outcome measure (i.e. headache days distributed as Poisson versus Gaussian) and 2) to evaluate improvement in power by controlling for between-subject variability using covariates (i.e., sex, headache type) in the treatment model. For the purposes of this application, we assumed that the data have a Gaussian distribution.

The parameters used in the program application of the CGRP trial were:

- Between-group mean difference in number of monthly headache days at Weeks 8-12: $\Delta = -1.15$ headache days (Between-group mean differences at Weeks 0-4 and Weeks 4-8: $\Delta = 0, -1.15$ headache days, respectively)
- Variability of number of monthly headache days: overall SD = 4.75, 4.50, 4.25 days for Visit 1, 2, 3, respectively
- Within-subject correlation of number of monthly headache days (adjacent, distal timepoints) = 0.7, 0.6, and 0.8, 0.7
- Sample size: N=162 per group

The group composition ratio was:

- 70:30 male:female
- 50:50 chronic:episodic headache

Time2 and Time3 were added as indicator variables (Visit 2: Time2=1, Time3=0; Visit 3: Time2=0, Time3=1)

Figure 6 shows the assumed change in mean number of monthly headache days over the three timepoints for the control and treatment groups of the CGRP study. For the control group, we did not expect a change in the number of monthly headache days over the three visits. However, for the treatment drug, we did expect a mean decrease of 1.15 headache days at visit 2 and for this change to maintain at visit 3.

Figure 6. CGRP Study expected monthly headache days at different visit periods¹.

¹ Error bars represent the standard deviations (SDs) around each mean number of monthly headache days at each timepoint. Visit 1: Weeks 0-4; Visit 2: Weeks 4-8; and Visit 3: Weeks 8-12 of the CGRP study.

To assess power, we tested three different treatment models for CGRP (**Table 2**). Given a higher number of headache days expected (11-13 days per month) in the participants, a model with an assumed Gaussian distribution can be used as an approximation of a model with a Poisson distribution. First, we tested two different linear models that used the last timepoint data only. Model 1 is a reduced model, where only treatment was the predictor variable. Model 2 added the covariates of sex and headache type to Model 1. We found that the addition of the covariates to the model provided better, but less than optimal power (0.66 vs 0.34). By inclusion of these variables, the model controls for between-subject variability resulting from sex and headache type (chronic, episodic) distributional differences in headache days which represent nuisance factors. As a result, a more precise estimation of treatment effect is obtained and, consequently, power is increased. Lastly, Model 3 was a linear mixed effects model using all the available data from the 3 timepoints. A random effect term (1|SubjectID) was included in the model to account for repeated measures in each subject. Out of the three models, Model 3 provided the most robust power (corr=0.7: 0.73 vs 0.66; corr=0.8: 0.84 vs. 0.64). The reason for this increase in power is additional control of between-subject variability (i.e., any difference in headache days occurring between subjects not the result of treatment). By the addition of this added level of control, estimation of the treatment effect at Weeks 8-12 is made more precise and power increases.

Table 2. CGRP Power Simulation Results¹

N per group = 162	corr = 0.7	corr = 0.8
Model 1 (linear; data: Week 8-12 (last timepoint only)) $Y \sim \mathbf{Trt}$	0.34	0.34
Model 2 (linear; data: Week 8-12 (last timepoint only)) $Y \sim \mathbf{Trt} + \text{sex} + \text{HAtype}$	0.66	0.64
Model 3 (LMM; data includes all 3 timepoints) $Y(t) \sim \mathbf{Trt} + \text{Time2} + \text{Time3} + \text{Trt}:\text{Time2}$ $+ \mathbf{Trt}:\text{Time3} + (1 \text{SubjectID})$	0.73	0.84

¹Model 1 and Model 2 were both linear models that only used the data from the last timepoint. Model 2 included the covariates of sex and headache type (HAtype), which improved the power value, compared to Model 1 (the most reduced model). Model 3 was a linear mixed effects model that used all of the simulated data from all three timepoints. Model 3 provided the most power for both within-subject correlations, as it took into consideration the between-subject variability with the (1|SubjectID) term. Based on comparable programming steps shown in Figure 4, the bootstrap used for this simulation included 1000 replicates where the t-statistics for the treatment effect (bold term indicated in each of the respective models in Table 2) was examined assuming a two-sided test and an $\alpha=0.05$.

4. Discussion

This power simulation program allows one to create simulated datasets that more directly reflect the study setup and study characteristics, and also allows one to calculate power by computationally using R software. We have demonstrated the application of this tool to evaluate power in three different clinical trials. Various study characteristics—either known or assumed—were utilized to simulate datasets that would approximate study data obtained from these trials. Based on assumptions about the models used to evaluate the primary outcome measure of these trials and known statistical properties, power was obtained. We would like to highlight that the program potentially offers flexibility and improved estimation of power over standard software options in clinical trial design and pre-data analysis.

Applications of the program were focused on studies where multivariate normal distributions were assumed for the primary outcome measure. However, the program is adaptable and data can be generated to reflect different assumed distributions of the primary outcome measure (e.g., poisson, binary, ordinal). Although our simulations did not examine study attrition, which is a reality for most clinical trials and a key aspect for estimating sample size/power, the program could be easily adapted to model and examine patient dropout. For example, data could be simulated to reflect data missing at random or modeled with respect to different variables included in the simulated data, or as the result of unmeasured variables.

The applications we have shown illustrate the flexibility of the program with respect to key assumptions regarding the variability of the primary outcome or within-subject correlation, which can vary with respect to time and, although not demonstrated here, with respect to treatment group. Moreover, we showed the flexibility of our method that allowed for inclusion of covariates in models of the primary outcome measure—a feature typically not available

in standard packages. The program is intuitive and user-friendly in terms of the different steps for incorporating different elements of the study at the data-generation stage, modeling stage, and inferential (power) stage.

Future steps will include creating multiple simulated datasets for each clinical trial application, in order to assess variability in power estimates, which is particularly applicable in situations given finite-sample variability. Additions can be made to the program to assess patient drop-out on study power as previously mentioned. Lastly, non-normal distributions will be included to allow for less restrictive assumptions of the primary outcome measure under investigation.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, this power simulation program can be used to compare the power values of different combinations of parameter assumptions and also to compare the power values of different possible treatment models of interest. The program assesses power given data that more directly reflect the actual study data and analytic strategies applied to the data. The enhanced flexibility of this approach also allows for the examination of power based on demographic or diagnostic information (e.g., severe v. mild insomnia) (i.e., differential treatment effects). This program is user-friendly and can be applied to a variety of study designs, not only to clinical trials.

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References

- Arnold, B. F., et al. (2011). "Simulation methods to estimate design power: an overview for applied research." *BMC Med Res Methodol* 11: 94.
- Beng, M. H., et al. (2021). "How Large a Study Is Needed to Detect TKA Revision Rate Reductions Attributable to Robotic or Navigated Technologies? A Simulation-based Power Analysis." *Clin Orthop Relat Res* 479: 2350-2361.
- Dorey, F. J. (2011). "In Brief: Statistics in Brief: Statistical Power: What Is It and When Should It Be Used?" *Clin Orthop Relat Res* 469: 619-620.
- Ensor, J., et al. (2018). "Simulation-based power calculations for planning a two-stage individual participant data meta-analysis." *BMC Med Res Methodol* 18(1): 41.
- Henry M. Jackson Foundation for the Advancement of Military Medicine. Internet-guided Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Insomnia in Military Service Members With History of TBI. *ClinicalTrials.gov* identifier: NCT04377009. Updated August 21, 2023. Accessed September 13, 2023. <https://classic.clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT04377009>.
- Henry M. Jackson Foundation for the Advancement of Military Medicine. Internet-guided Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Insomnia in Military Service Members With History of TBI. *ClinicalTrials.gov* identifier: NCT05147506. Updated August 21, 2023. Accessed September 13, 2023. <https://classic.clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT05147506>.
- Henry M. Jackson Foundation for the Advancement of Military Medicine. Internet-guided Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Insomnia in Military Service Members With History of TBI. *ClinicalTrials.gov* identifier: NCT05049057. Updated August 21, 2023. Accessed September 13, 2023. <https://classic.clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT05049057>.
- Huang, C., P. Li and C. R. Martin (2022). "Simplification or simulation: Power calculation in clinical trials." *Contemp Clin Trials* 113: 106663.
- Kumle, L., M. L. Vo and D. Draschkow (2021). "Estimating power in (generalized) linear mixed models: An open introduction and tutorial in R." *Behav Res Methods* 53(6): 2528-2543.
- Ma, J., et al. (2016). "Power Analysis for Population-Based Longitudinal Studies Investigating Gene-Environment Interactions in Chronic Diseases: A Simulation Study." *PLoS One* 11(2): e0149940.
- Morris, T. P., I. R. White and M. J. Crowther (2019). "Using simulation studies to evaluate statistical methods." *Stat Med* 38(11): 2074-2102.
- Peterlin, B. L., S. S. Nijjar and G. E. Tietjen (2011). "Post-traumatic stress disorder and migraine: epidemiology, sex differences, and potential mechanisms." *Headache* 51(6): 860-868.